

FIBER COATINGS FOR A SAPPHIRE/GAMMA-TiAl MMC, UTILIZING DUCTILE AND BARRIER METALLIC LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

A ductile Nb/Y coating concept on fibers was used to fabricate sapphire (Al_2O_3)/gamma-TiAl MMCs. Nb provided ductility, and protected the fiber from reaction induced damage. Y played the role of a barrier layer. Ti was shown to be extremely detrimental to the fiber, and Y was effective in preventing Ti from reaching the fiber. Pushed out fibers showed that the interface had separated cleanly at the alumina/Nb interface. Fracture surfaces showed limited debonding, in agreement with a normal interface separation criterion. However, the length of debonding was small, and is explained on the basis of the ratio of interface toughness to fiber toughness. A dual combination of coated fibers is suggested, and there are possible applications of the concept in more ductile Ti-alloy matrices.

INTRODUCTION

Reinforcement options are being considered for intermetallic systems with low ductility, both to extend the range of temperature applications, and to incorporate a degree of damage tolerance in the material. To gain some fundamental understanding in this area, a gamma-TiAl matrix based metal matrix composite (MMC) was considered, since there are applications where payoffs from a compositing approach can be significant. Attention was focused on ceramic fibers that possess good high-temperature properties, so as to obtain improved creep resistance of the MMC. Alternate approaches have relied on ductile metallic reinforcements, such as Nb, which can provide low temperature toughness improvement through ductile ligaments in the crack wake [1]. Such ductile reinforcements also are useful, but provide little or no improvement in high-temperature strength and creep resistance, and was not considered in this study.

A disadvantage of gamma TiAl compared with conventional Ti-alloys is that the thermal expansion coefficient is high. For example, the chord expansion coefficient between room temperature and 1000 C is approximately $12.3 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ for gamma-TiAl [2], compared with approximately $10.7 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ for the Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn (Ti-15-3) beta alloy. These values may be compared with two common fibers, namely SCS-6 fibers and sapphire alumina fibers, with expansion coefficients of $4.7 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ and $8.3 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The calculated room temperature (RT) stresses that result from these expansion coefficients for the two types of fibers are provided in Table 1, for a 15 volume percent MMC. It is notable that the matrix around the fibers had yielded to a plastic strain of approximately 0.8% for SiC fibers and to 0.25% for the case of alumina fibers. An elastic-plastic concentric cylinder model was used for the analyses, and a stress-free temperature of 950 C was assumed. The low flow stress of the matrix, approximately 450 MPa at RT, also contributed to early yielding; in fact, yielding initiated at a temperature of 450 C during the cool-down process. Considering the limited ductility of gamma-TiAl (typically 1-2%), SiC fibers are therefore less favorable as a reinforcement option from a thermal stress perspective. Accordingly, in this work, attention was focused on Saphikon™ sapphire fibers, with an as-received strength of approximately 2800 MPa and a fiber radius of approximately 120 μm .

Table 1. Thermal Stress Calculations for 15 Volume % Fibers in a Gamma-TiAl MMC++

Fibers	Axial Fiber Stress, MPa	Radial Matrix Stress at Interface	Tangential Matrix Stress at Interface	Axial Matrix Stress at Interface	Tangential Matrix Plastic Strain at Interface	Axial Matrix Plastic Strain at Interface
Alumina	-1100	-339	185	22*	0.26% +	0.06%
SiC	-2000	-407	123	-23 **	0.60% #	0.20%

* Far from interface the axial matrix stress is 200 MPa; ** Far from interface, the axial matrix stress is 400 MPa; + Radial plastic strain was -0.22%; # radial plastic strain was -0.8%
 ++ Stress-free temperature of 950 C was assumed.

APPROACH

Fiber Coating Requirements

Titanium is known to react with alumina [3], and evidence will be provided later of reaction induced damage. Consequently, it is important to develop suitable coatings that can minimize damage of fibers. Various desired attributes of a coating system include:

- (i) It must protect the fiber from reaction-induced loss of strength.
- (ii) It should preferably be beneficial in reducing thermal stresses, although this may not be a critical requirement.
- (iii) It must allow for limited debonding, so as to reduce stress concentrations arising either from premature fiber fracture, or from matrix cracking.
- (iv) It should not act as a crack initiation site.
- (v) It should have some normal bond strength, to provide strength and creep resistance in the transverse direction.
- (vi) It should not dissolve in the matrix.

Damage Tolerance, and Creep and Transverse-Strength Considerations

Concentrating on item (iii) initially, it may be noted that a very weak bond is not necessarily the best solution. The reason is that it is detrimental to load transfer and longitudinal creep resistance at high temperatures, and also transverse strengths are seriously degraded.

Consider Figure 1, which is a sketch of a matrix crack approaching a ceramic fiber. Calculations performed by Gupta, Argon, and Suo [4] indicate that the σ_{xx} stress at the fiber-matrix interface can be sufficient to cause fiber-matrix debonding, even before the crack reaches the fiber. Such debonding indeed has been observed in the SCS6/Ti-15-3 system under fatigue loading [5]. The requirement for such debonding depends sensitively on the Dundurs parameter, α , for a bimetallic interface, namely:

$$\alpha = (E_f - E_m) / (E_f + E_m),$$

where E_f and E_m are fiber and matrix modulus, respectively. Considering modulus values of 166 GPa and 350 GPa for the gamma-TiAl matrix and alumina fiber, respectively, the results in [4] suggest that the condition for debonding at the interface, before arrival of the matrix crack tip at the fiber surface, is satisfied if the normal strength of the interface, σ_b , is less than about 0.4 times the fiber strength, σ_f . As will be explained shortly, a Nb fiber coating was considered from reaction considerations, and reported normal bond strengths for the alumina/Nb system lie around 80-120 MPa [12]. Using the higher number, and assuming a radial compressive stress at the interface of approximately 340 MPa (see Table 1), the ratio of σ_b/σ_f is calculated to be 0.16, so that normal debonding is indeed predicted.

When the matrix crack does reach the fiber, however, it also is necessary for the crack to debond over a sufficient distance, so that the stress concentration is reduced, through crack bridging, by the time the matrix crack arrives at the next fiber. The toughness parameter, namely, G_i/G_f , can be invoked at this time, and it follows from the work of Hutchinson [6,7] that this value should be less than about 0.25 if interface debonding has to be maintained, without fracture of the fiber.

Here G_i and G_f are the strain energy release rates for the interface and fiber respectively. While G_f for sapphire is estimated to be around 25 J/m², based on a fracture toughness of 3.5 MPa√m, the interface toughness of the Nb/alumina system is not known a priori, for the processing conditions used in this study. In addition, it is shown in [8] that sliding of the fiber-matrix interface contributes an additional term, $G_{\text{friction}} = \tau^2 l / r E_f$, to the interface toughness, where τ is the friction stress, r is the fiber radius, and l is the length over which debonding has taken place. This expression indicates that a low friction stress is desirable, and in reference [9,10], a carbon coating was used on sapphire in a gamma-TiAl matrix to obtain a low friction stress. While such an approach is attractive from a damage tolerant perspective, we have already cited two important deficiencies. In particular, note that some transverse loads are always anticipated to be present in a structure, and a weak transverse strength could be extremely detrimental to structural integrity.

The approach that was taken in this work was to rely on a *ductile coating* around the fibers, in particular a Nb coating. Nb is ductile, with a flow stress of around 100 MPa at RT. This approach may only provide limited damage tolerance in the presence of a large dominant crack, since friction stress may not be low enough to cause debonding over a few fiber diameters, and thus help in crack bridging. On the other hand, if the stress intensity factor of an advancing crack is reasonably low, such as one resulting from a processing flaw size of 1-2 fiber diameters at the flow stress of the matrix, then the ductile coating can be quite effective. Simple calculations, using the formula, $\sigma = K/\sqrt{2\pi r}$, and assuming a maximum fiber stress of 2800 MPa indicate that as long as the stress intensity factor is less than approximately 7MPa√m, a 1μm thick ductile coating should be able to prevent failure of the fiber from an advancing matrix crack.

The other scenario under which the ductile coating approach can provide adequate damage tolerance is where a premature fiber break must be prevented from failing an adjacent fiber. The work of He et al.[11] has shown that global load sharing (i.e., prevention of adjacent fiber break through stress concentration) can be realized so long as the friction stress is less than about 10% of the fiber strength. For a fiber strength of 2800 MPa, this implies that either the interface strength, or the flow stress of the ductile coating must be less than 280 MPa. This situation is anticipated for the coating under consideration. An additional advantage is that because the coating is ductile, it would not be a nucleation site for cracks, unlike approaches that rely on brittle coatings. When loaded in the transverse direction, the reasonable bond strength of 80-120 MPa would prevent debonding, and the coating would flow and provide displacement compatibility with the surrounding matrix.

Chemistry Considerations and Requirement for a Barrier Layer

As already indicated, prevention of fiber damage is a foremost consideration in coating selection. A literature survey indicated that Nb is a good candidate in this regard, and NbO_x has been found to epitaxially deposit on sapphire surfaces [12]. Interfaces are generally clean, except at very high processing temperatures (>1400 C), where Nb etching at alumina grain boundaries is observed. Fracture is reported to be at the interface, indicating that chemical activity of the species probably is insufficient to cause any significant damage of the alumina.

The problem with Nb is that it can readily dissolve in the Ti-aluminide matrix, so that if a barrier layer is not used, then the coating layer will be lost. More importantly, a consequence of having only a single Nb layer is that Ti from the matrix would diffuse through the Nb coating, and cause damage to the fiber. A ceramic barrier coating is one approach, but disadvantages include damage of the Nb layer, as well as the fact that the ceramic would be weak and be a source for crack initiation in the low-ductility matrix. A metallic barrier layer is therefore desired. Its important attributes would include prevention of Ti diffusion, be fairly insoluble in the TiAl matrix, retain a degree of ductility, and not melt at the MMC processing temperature.

Fortunately yttrium does appear to provide this blend of rather wide range of characteristics. The phase diagrams for the Ti-Y system and the Nb-Y systems are reproduced from [13] in Figure 2, and the following characteristics may be noted. First, for the Nb-Y system, there is absolutely no solubility between the elements up to the eutectic temperature of 1470 C. In other words, such a layer would prevent any diffusion of Nb into the surrounding matrix. Second, for the Ti-Y

system, the solubilities are essentially zero up to 870 C, after which there is some solubility. At a processing temperature of 1200 C, the solubility of Ti in Y would increase to about 1.5 atomic percent, but this may be insufficient to cause widespread diffusion of Ti from the matrix into the Y layer, and then on to the fiber through the intervening Nb layer. Accordingly, the dual Nb/Y layer was selected for the study, and this is schematically represented in Figure 3; an additional Ti-40Nb layer was included, to prevent oxidation of the Y during handling before consolidation.

EXPERIMENTS

A foil-fiber-foil approach was used for consolidating the MMCs. Gamma TiAl foils of approximate thickness 0.25 mm were electric discharge machined from a forged ingot of composition Ti-47Al-1.8Nb-1.6Cr-0.4Mn-0.5Si. The forged ingot had a duplex microstructure of lamellar and equiaxed gamma grains, and possessed an elongation of approximately 2% at RT. The foils, of approximate size 7cm x 2.5 cm, were electropolished to depths of approximately 25 μm from each face to remove oxide scales, prior to being used for the MMC consolidation runs.

Sapphire fibers were coated with a triplex Nb/Y/Ti-40Nb coating, using a sputter deposition unit. The thickness of the coatings were approximately 2μm for each layer, but experiments with 1μm coatings suggested that it also may be adequate.

Single-ply MMCs were consolidated, with two additional gamma-TiAl foils utilized as back up plates. Consolidation conditions were determined using the approach outlined in Goetz et al.[14], wherein consolidation is governed by creep flow of the matrix over an average creep strain, ϵ_{av} , (~ 0.6) required for complete consolidation. The following equations are relevant:

$$\begin{aligned} d\epsilon_{av}/dt &= 1.2/t^* & t^* &= \text{time of consolidation}; & \epsilon_{av} &= \text{strain}; & t &= \text{time} \\ P &= 1.6\sigma & P &= \text{HIP pressure}; & \sigma &= \text{the stress on the matrix} \\ d\epsilon/dt &= 7042 \exp\{-47619/T^\circ K\} \sigma^4 & d\epsilon/dt &= \text{secondary creep rate, 1/sec}; & \sigma &= \text{MPa} \end{aligned}$$

The above secondary-creep equation for gamma TiAl was obtained from [15], using creep data generated between 800 C and 1000 C. Based on a number of trial runs, a temperature of 1175 C was selected such that it was only slightly above the eutectoid temperature, and the time was short enough to prevent excessive reactions. For a HIP pressure of 82.7 MPa (12 ksi) used in this investigation, the equations provide a consolidation time of approximately 76 minutes. In actuality, a total hold of 90 minutes at 1175 C was utilized. During the cool-down period, the specimen was held at 950 C for 0.5 hr. to allow some relaxation of the residual stresses.

Following consolidation, the microstructures were evaluated, and microprobe traces were obtained to assess the effectiveness of the coating layers. Interface shear strengths were obtained using approximately 0.9 mm thick samples in push-out tests. Pushed out fibers were analyzed to determine the interface failure location; i.e., at which interface debonding occurred. Limited tensile tests were performed, and fracture surfaces were examined to determine the extent of fiber bridging and the location of interface fracture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

Figure 4a shows the microstructure from an initial HIP-run (No.HP3), and it illustrates that full consolidation was achieved. The layer adjacent to the fiber is Nb, and the darker layer is Y. The layer of Y suggests that indeed it did maintain its identity, in agreement with the phase diagrams. A close inspection revealed that the coating had broken off at a number of places, and in these areas there was significant erosion of the alumina fiber. This is illustrated better in Figure 4b. The fiber erosion is likely caused by aggressive reaction with Ti, since coating failure allowed easy access of Ti from the matrix to the fiber. Clearly coating integrity must be maintained.

The peeling of the coating also was observed when handling the fibers before consolidation. An effective solution was to obtain some bond strength by heating the coated fibers in high vacuum at 1175 C for half an hour, before incorporating them in the composite. This was successful, and

Figure 5 illustrates intactness of the coating for HIP-run HP6. In this case, thinner coating layers were applied ($\sim 1\mu\text{m Nb}$, and $0.5\mu\text{m Y}$).

Figure 6b illustrates the elemental concentration profile for a horizontal line scan taken along the arrow in Figure 6a, for a fiber which was polished at a very shallow angle to the surface. The section has just grazed the Nb coating, and the alumina fiber lies just below the surface. The darker bands on either side of the white central region correspond to the Y layer, and the slightly brighter band next to it is also primarily Y with possibly yttrium aluminides. Figure 6b shows the anticipated concentration profiles. For example, note that the Nb concentration drops very rapidly where the Y levels start rising; the slight dish of the Nb concentration in the middle is likely caused by the alumina fiber below the surface. The Y concentration, on the other hand, shows the anticipated two humps. The Ti concentration shows that it is essentially absent until the Y concentration drops, indicating that the Y barrier has indeed been very effective in preventing flow of Ti to the fiber. Finally, not much can be said about the Al concentration, since there is about 48 at% Al in the matrix, and it is present in the alumina fiber. Note that both Nb and Y form complex aluminides, and the dotted microstructure likely corresponds to those phases. No attempt was made to determine the composition or structure of the particulates.

Interface Tests

Push-out tests appeared to show crack initiation from both the top and bottom surfaces for the 0.9 mm thick samples, this being surmised from the load-displacement curves and residual displacement analyses of partially loaded fibers [8]. An average interface shear strength of 155 MPa was obtained, and this is comparable with a debond strength 145 MPa determined by Koss et al.[16] for a sapphire/Nb system. In this latter case, the thermal radial stresses are significantly less than for the current system, yet it is interesting to note quite similar bond strengths. Reported data for carbon coated sapphire in gamma TiAl are: approximately 30 MPa for a colloidal C/alumina coating, and approximately 100 MPa for a carbon black/alumina coating[9]. The outer alumina layer was utilized to prevent reaction of C with TiAl, but they can be potent crack sites.

Figure 7 shows a fiber that had been pushed out of the back face. The cylindrical surface of the pushed out fiber is quite smooth, and energy dispersive analyses of X-rays (EDAX) showed consistently that Nb was essentially absent on the cylindrical surfaces. Rather, traces of Ti were observed, and these usually were localized at the poker marks on the surfaces. As indicated earlier, some Ti can make its way to the fiber surface, and leave behind its permanent imprint through reactions. In addition to Ti, traces of Y also were observed on the fiber surface. The origin for this is not clear, since the phase diagram suggests no solubility of Y in Nb. Overall, it may be concluded from these observations that shear interface fracture largely occurs at the alumina/Nb interface, which must therefore be the weakest link in the system. The cleanliness of the fracture suggest that Nb is a compatible system for protection of the sapphire fiber.

Tensile Tests

Figure 8 is a stress-strain curve from a tensile test at RT. The coupon contained approximately five volume percent fibers, so that as anticipated, the modulus value lies within the range of scatter for monolithic gamma-TiAl. The strength of 350 MPa was lower than that of the monolithic panel (~ 460 MPa); however, neat fiberless specimens were not evaluated to determine how the MMC processing affected the tensile properties. Part of the strength debit could be from oxygen pickup during foil preparation, and from the fiber during consolidation. It also is noteworthy that the yield strength was quite low; however, confirmatory tests are needed.

Figure 9a shows the fracture surface of a tensile specimen, and it is encouraging to note a limited amount of pull-out; the crack propagated from the bottom to the top of the figure. Figure 9b is a close-up of one of the fibers, and note how the Nb layer has plastically pulled away from the fiber. Similar to the pushed out fiber, the fiber surface showed no evidence of Nb. Rather, only small amounts of Ti were detected on surface, and these are believed to have given the exposed fibers the rough appearance. The pull out length was very small, but is consistent with a large value of G_i/G_f . Even for zero inherent G_i value, the friction stress contributes a G_i of 15.4 J/m^2

for a debond length of one fiber diameter (see earlier discussion). This easily puts the G_i/G_f value above 0.25, leading to fracture of the fiber. Since G_o_i for the Nb/alumina interface is anticipated to be much larger than zero, the tendency for fiber fracture is further enhanced. A Mo interlayer might reduce G_o_i values, and can be substituted for Nb, since the phase diagrams for Mo-Y and Nb-Y are similar. However, Mo is likely to possess less ductility, and its reactivity with the fiber has to be evaluated. As indicated earlier, the ductile layer concept for damage tolerance is valid for only those applications where stress intensity factors are small, such as from processing related flaws or from adjacent fiber breaks. For greater damage tolerance, a weak interface would be preferable.

CONCLUSIONS

The experiments illustrate that the Nb/Y combination is an effective interlayer system for sapphire fibers. Although fiber strength tests were not performed, the pushed out fibers and fracture surfaces suggest minimal damage of the fiber due to Nb. On the other hand, Ti is extremely damaging, in that it leads to pucker marks and significant erosion of the fiber. The Nb/Y system aids considerably in avoiding this deleterious effect of Ti. Pushed out fibers and fibers protruding on the fracture surfaces showed essentially no evidence of Nb, suggesting interface fracture occurs cleanly through the alumina/Nb interface.

The limited fiber pull-outs are in agreement with the normal stress criterion for debonding. On the other hand, the length of pull-out was extremely small, pointing to the fact that G_i/G_f is quite high. One possible approach for actual applications might be a dual combination of coated fibers, with C coated fibers for tolerance to impact damage and large cracks, and ductile metal coated fibers for high temperature strength, transverse properties, and tolerance to small flaws. Finally, this Nb/Y concept would also be very useful for more ductile Ti-alloy reinforcements with alumina fibers, since brittle matrix cracks would not occur, the main requirement being global load sharing and adequate transverse strength.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Materials Directorate, Wright Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, through contract No. F33615-91-C-5663 to UES, Inc.. The assistance of Dr. R. Bhattacharya in fiber coating, Mr. Carl Boehlert in tensile testing, Mr. Tim Campbell in specimen preparation, Mr. Mark Dodd in HIP-ing, and Mr. J. Henry in microprobe analysis are sincerely acknowledged.

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Figure 1. Sketch showing a matrix crack approaching a fiber-matrix interface.

Figure 2. Phase diagrams for the Ti-Y and Nb-Y systems, showing extremely low solubility of the elements in each other.

Figure 3. Sketch showing the coating system used in this study.

Figure 4. (a) Microstructure of the Sapphire/gamma-TiAl system, showing consolidation of the MMC. (b) Higher magnification micrograph for a fiber whose coating was cracked.

Figure 5. Micrograph showing that coating integrity is maintained for a pre-heat-treated fiber.

Figure 6. a) Longitudinal section of the coated fiber, with a microprobe line scan taken at the location of the arrow. (b) Elemental concentration showing that the Y coating indeed is effective in preventing flow of Ti inwards, and Nb outwards.

Figure 7. Micrograph of the pushed out fiber. EDAX analysis shows only Al and traces of Ti on the cylindrical surface.

Figure 8. Result of tensile test of the MMC at RT.

Figure 9. Low and high magnification micrographs of the fracture surface. Note the debonding of the Nb.